

Solvent free, highly chemoselective *N* and *O*-acylation on silica and silica magnesium oxide : A recyclable solid surface

Pranab Ghosh* and Amitava Mandal

Department of Chemistry, University of North Bengal, Darjeeling-734 013, West Bengal, India

E-mail : pizy12@yahoo.com Fax : 91-353-2699001

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Abstract : Silica or silica/magnesium oxide mixed surface mediates the *N* and *O*-acylation, benzylation or sulfonylation of hosts of substrates under solvent free conditions at ambient temperature with high chemoselectivity.

Keywords : *N* and *O*-acylation, silica or silica/magnesium, Green chemistry, chemoselective.

Introduction

N and *O*-acylation of amines and alcohols represents fundamental reactions in organic synthesis and are very common as a protective group and in various biosynthetic phenomena¹⁻⁵. Moreover, these reactions have a biomimetic importance because acylation of xenobiotics is a metabolic pathway that increases lipophilicity. Amides and their derivatives are important functionalities in various natural products and synthetic targets^{6,7}. They are widely used as basic intermediates to prepare solvents, fine chemicals, pharmaceuticals, agrochemicals and catalysts for polymerization^{8,9}. *N*-Acylbenzotriazoles find use as neutral acylating reagents for the preparation of primary, secondary and tertiary amides¹⁰. On the other hand, esters of alcohols represent a useful class of organic compounds which find versatile applications as key reagents in organic, bio-organic, heterocyclic and medicinal chemistry¹¹. During the multistep synthesis including the synthesis of complex natural products⁶, the efficiency of the synthetic protocol often depends largely on protection of the selective functional group or groups. Therefore; the development of new synthetic method to prepare these *N* and *O*-acyl derivatives has become the goal of many research groups over the years^{12,13}.

Plenty of synthetic methods exist for acylation of amines and alcohols besides their classical method of preparation. Acylation of amines and alcohols is usually performed by employing either acid anhydrides or acid chlorides in the presence of stoichiometric amount of bases such as 4-(dimethyl amino)pyridine or 4-pyrrolidino pyridine (4-PPY)^{14,15}, tertiary amine^{16,17} and tributyl phos-

phine¹⁸. Acylation has also been reported to achieve by using indium(III) chloride¹⁹, LiClO₄²⁶, Mg(ClO₄)²¹. Benzylation of amines using benzoyl chloride, benzoic anhydride, benzoyl tetrazole, benzoyl cyanide has been achieved by bases like pyridine, triethyl amine and sodium hydroxide²²⁻²⁶. The solvents commonly chosen for these reactions are methylene chloride, acetonitrile and tetrahydrofuran. Thus apart from some operational disadvantages like moisture sensitivity and high costs of many of those catalysts; the procedures using toxic metal derivatives as catalysts and chlorinated hydrocarbons or other toxic solvents also do not satisfy the requirements of green chemistry.

With the advent of solid phase organic synthesis and increasing popularity for heterogeneous solvent-free applications, use of inorganic solid supports has been reported for *N* and *O*-acylation reactions. For example, acylation of amines and alcohols with acid anhydrides are reported to carry out by Ac₂O-Py/basic alumina²⁷, montmorillonite K-10 and KSF^{28,29}, zeolite H-FER³⁰, zeolite HSZ-360³¹, KF-alumina³² and heteropoly acid catalyst (H₆P₂W₁₈O₆₂·24H₂O)³³. Acylation has also been carried out with carboxylic acids in presence of acid catalysts, such as yttria-zirconia-based Lewis acid³⁴. Apart from these catalysts, TMSOTf³⁵ and TMSCl³⁶ have also been used as efficient catalysts for acetylation of alcohols. Neat reaction for acylation of alcohols, amines and thiols under solvent free and catalyst free conditions has been reported by Ranu *et al.*³⁷. Most of these procedures including the neat reaction protocol reported to date are very general towards the functional groups concerned and

so suffers from lack of selectivity. The Lewis acids are efficient catalysts but most of them are wasteful being hydrolyzed at the time of workup of the reaction mixture. Some of them are quite expensive as well. Very recently Clark *et al.*³⁸ has reported the preparation of amides via *N*-acylation of amines under microwave irradiation using a starbon acid catalyst and acetic acid as the acylation reagent. Heterogeneous acid catalyst is useful but being acidic in nature is environmentally harmful.

In search for greener synthetic protocol and considering the above limitations viz. lack of selectivity, versatility, non-corrosive and reusable solid supports to promote organic reactions is a genuine demand in contemporary organic synthesis. Silica and magnesium oxide; a class of inexpensive and non-corrosive solid support, has been used as efficient reaction medium for a variety of organic reactions³⁹⁻⁵⁰. Silica gel is a porous, amorphous form of silica and is radically different from other silica-based materials due to its unique internal structure. It is composed of a vast network of interconnected microscopic pores. Thus, we planned to explore this remarkable efficacy of silica gel and were delighted to see the very recent report of both mono- and bis-alkylation of primary amines on silica gel surface efficiently under different conditions⁴¹. In this communication, we disclose highly efficient, chemoselective and expeditious protocols for acylation, benzylation and sulfonylation of amines, alcohols and heterocyclic amines under mild and solvent free conditions at room temperature. Chemoselectivity of the protocol was also tested by carrying out the reactions in presence of other reactive functionalities. A variety of aromatic and aliphatic amines and alcohols including diamines, diols and heterocyclic amines bearing acidic hydrogens have been tested for acylation reactions to develop practically general protocols. No other catalysts or solvents were required and reactions were carried out smoothly at room temperature. Acylation and sulfonylation of amines are carried out using silica gel HF-254 (for tlc) and the same reactions on alcohols are performed by using 1 : 1 mixture of silica gel and magnesium oxide, at ambient temperature under solvent free condition without using any other bases or catalysts (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

Organic reactions catalysed or mediated by solid supports remains a strategic field in chemistry because of their implications in industry and environment. To explore the generality, selectivity and scope; structurally diverse amines and alcohols were subjected to acylation, benzylation and sulfonylation under solvent free conditions at ambient temperature using corresponding acid halides. This procedure is simple and extremely useful for the preparation of various types of amides and esters at room temperature and showed high degree of chemoselectivity.

The protocol for *N*-acylation was developed and optimised on the basis of a model study by choosing a variety of solid supports, aniline as the substrate and acetyl chloride as the acylating agent (*vide infra*). In a typical reaction procedure 1 : 2.5 molar ratio of aniline and acetyl chloride was mixed with previously activated solid support (500 mg mmol⁻¹) and the solid mixtures were stirred at room temperature for a varying period of time. The product composition were checked by taking a small amount from the reaction mixture in methanol and analysed by HPLC.

Table 1 shows a study of *N*-acylation of aniline on various solid supports using acetyl chloride as the acylating agent, which shows that acetylation of aniline is highly facilitated on silica at room temperature among the other solid supports studied.

Table 1. Reaction of aniline with acetyl chloride on various solid supports at room temperature

Entry	Solid support	Time (min)	Aniline (%)	Product (%)
1	Silica gel GF-254	30	71.81	28.19
2	"	60	67.98	32.02
3	"	120	57.77	42.23
4	Molecular sieve, 4 Å	30	83.99	16.01
5	"	60	82.20	17.80
6	"	120	75.16	24.84
7	Neutral alumina	30	94.20	5.80
8	"	60	91.62	8.38
9	"	120	86.01	13.99
10	Silica gel HF-254	30	15.61	84.39
11	"	60	6.39	94.17

% Yield calculated from HPLC.

While investigating the acylating ability of the various acylating agents available, it was observed that acetyl chloride could acylate aniline completely on silica gel HF-254 within 1 h and at room temperature (Table 2). We then studied the efficiency of the number of equiva-

Table 2. Reaction of aniline with various acylating agents on silica at room temperature

Entry	Acylating agent	Time (min)	Aniline (%)	Product (%)
1	Acetic anhydride	30	94.78	5.22
2	"	60	89.66	10.34
3	"	120	89.54	10.46
4	Acetic acid	30	97.19	2.81
5	"	60	93.86	6.14
6	"	120	91.99	8.01
7	Acetyl chloride	30	15.61	84.39
8	"	60	6.39	94.17
9	"	120	Nil	96.29

% Yield calculated from HPLC.

lents of acetyl chloride required (Fig. 1) and find that with freshly redistilled acetyl chloride one equivalent is

Fig. 1. Variation of % yield with respect to molar proportion of acetyl chloride in the feed after 30 min.

sufficient to carry out excellent yields. A further study was also done to find out the minimum weight of the solid support need to take for the transformation and the results are summarized in Fig. 2.

Thus the above study indicated that amongst the solid supports tried, silica gel HF-254 appeared to be the best for acylating aniline selectively using acid halides as the acylating reagent. Furthermore, only 500 mg of solid

Fig. 2. Variation of % yield with respect to the changes in the amount of solid support after 30 min.

support is sufficient to carry out the conversion of 1 mmol of aniline to the corresponding amide by the use of 1 mmol of acetyl chloride. Encouraged by these findings and using these optimised conditions, as elaborated in the above portion, various types of substituted amides were synthesized from a series of amines and acid halides in excellent yields (Table 3). In order to achieve the general applicability of this method the protocol was attempted on structurally and electronically diverse nature of amines using different acid halides. The results as summarized in Table 3 indicated that all the reactions proceeded efficiently and the desired amides were obtained in excellent yields in a very short time with a remarkable reactivity and selectivity.

We first carried out this novel protocol with acetyl chloride (entry 1, 5, 8, 9, 11, 14, 15, 18, 22 and 23 of Table 3) and then successfully extended with benzoyl chloride (entry 3, 7, 12, 16, 17 and 21 of Table 3), chloroacetyl chloride (entry 2, 6, 19 and 20 of Table 3), benzoyl bromide (entry 4 and 10 of Table 3) and also with oxalyl chloride (entry 13 and 24 of Table 3).

As sulfonamides are extremely useful pharmaceutical compounds and exhibit a wide range of biological activities such as anticancer, anti-inflammatory, antiviral functions and HIV protease inhibitors⁵¹⁻⁵⁴, people have already reported the preparation of such type of compounds⁵⁵⁻⁵⁷ following different methods. Because of the simplicity of our method over the existing processes, we also extended our protocol on the sulfonamides, whereby a variety of heterocyclic sulfonamides were synthesised in a very good yield (entry 25-29 of Table 3). With best

Table 3. Selective acylation of various amides

Entry	Amine	Acid chloride	Time (h)	Yield of product (%)
1	Aniline	Acetyl chloride	1	94
2	"	Chloro acetyl chloride	1	92
3	"	Benzyl chloride	2.5	90
4	"	Benzyl bromide	3.5	88
5	4-Chloro aniline	Acetyl chloride	1.5	91
6	"	Chloro acetyl chloride	1.5	88
7	2-Hydroxy aniline	Benzyl chloride	2.5	72
8	4-Amino benzoic acid	Acetyl chloride	2.5	82
9	4-Hydroxy aniline	Acetyl chloride	2.5	82
10	4-Chloro aniline	Benzyl bromide	3	81
11	2-Bromo aniline	Acetyl chloride	1	96
12	2-Methyl aniline	Benzyl chloride	3	84
13	Aniline	Oxalyl chloride	0.5	80 ^a
14	Butyl amine	Acetyl chloride	1.5	74
15	Diphenyl amine	"	6.5	72
16	Ethyl butyl amine	Benzyl chloride	4	68
17	Piperidine	"	2.5	76
18	Morpholine	Acetyl chloride	3	84
19	1,2,3-Benzo triazole	Chloro acetyl chloride	3.5	86
20	"	Chloro acetyl chloride	2.5	82
21	Benzo imidazole	Benzyl chloride	2.5	76
22	"	Acetyl chloride	2.5	88
23	<i>o</i> -Phenylenediamine	"	2	86 ^a
24	"	Oxalyl chloride	0.5	84 ^a
25	1,2,3-Benzo triazole	4-Toluene sulfonyl chloride	3.5	78
26	"	Benzene sulfonyl chloride	3.0	82
27	Imidazole	Methane sulfonyl chloride	2.0	70
28	Phenyl hydrazene	4-Toluene sulfonyl chloride	4.0	74
29	2,4-DNP	"	48	64

% Yield refers to the isolated yield of the products.

^aBis-substitution has occurred.

of our knowledge this is probably the very first report of synthesizing substituted heterocyclic sulfonamides on silica HF-254 (for tlc) in a solvent free condition.

The chemoselectivity of this method is also noteworthy. Molecules having both amino and carboxylic acid groups, amino and phenolic -OH group afforded only the corresponding amide (entry 7, 8 and 9 of Table 3) and the carboxyl group or phenolic -OH groups remain intact. It was also observed that use of excess acid chlorides or long reaction time had not any effect on the monoselectivity or chemoselectivity of the reaction.

Such a remarkable reactivity and selectivity under this mild and simple reaction conditions on silica gel surface was unprecedented and encouraged us to extend the protocol on alcohols. However contrary to our expectation it took prolonged reaction time and the yield was also very poor. We then modified the process by mixing MgO with silica gel HF-254 (for tlc) in 1 : 1 ratio (w/w). This modification of the solid support made the reactions smoother with excellent yields and no side products have been isolated in any reaction. Both acylation and benzylation of naturally occurring secondary alcohols (entry 14–21 of Table 4) which are very often carried out

Table 4. Selective acylation of alcohols

Entry	Alcohol	Acyating agent	Time (h)	Yield (%)
1	Benzal alcohol	Acetyl chloride	2.5	87
2	"	Benzoyl chloride	4	80
3	"	Benzoyl bromide	4.5	78
4	"	Chloro acetyl chloride	2.5	78
5	2-Hydroxy benzyl alcohol	Acetyl chloride	2	80 ^a
6	Ethyl alcohol	"	1.5	88
7	<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	Benzoyl chloride	1.5	82
8	<i>n</i> -Octyl alcohol	Acetyl chloride	2	80
9	<i>n</i> -Dodecanol	"	1.5	78
10	2-Butanol	"	3.5	72
11	Cyclohexanol	"	3	86
12	"	Benzoyl chloride	4	76
13	"	Benzoyl bromide	4	72
14	Cholesterol	Acetyl chloride	3.5	86
15	"	Benzoyl chloride	4	82
16	"	Benzoyl bromide	5.5	72
17	28-Carbomethoxy-3-hydroxy lup-20(29)-ene	Acetyl chloride	4.5	84
18	"	Benzoyl chloride	5	86
19	16-DPA	Acetyl chloride	4	88
20	3,28-Dihydroxy lup-20(29)-ene	Acetyl chloride	4.5	88 ^b
21	Diosgenin	"	4	86

^aOnly the alcoholic hydroxyl group was converted to the corresponding acylated product but not the phenolic hydroxyl group.

^bDiacetylation was observed.

to protect the C-3 functionality during many transformations involving C-21 isopropenyl side chain, have also been accomplished in good yields within a short duration of time. In addition the acylation at C-28 alcohol was also tried (entry 20 of Table 4) and was found very much effective inspite of the strong steric hindrance offered by the ring systems (D and E rings).

The chemoselectivity of this procedure is also interesting to note e.g. the molecules having both phenolic and alcoholic -OH groups (entry 5 of Table 6) when treated with acid halides using our procedure, it is only the alcoholic -OH group which is being converted to acetate and not the phenolic one.

Recyclability is one of the most important aspects which satisfy the requirements of green chemistry. To examine the recyclability of silica and silica-magnesium oxide mixed surface (as the case may be), we recovered the solid sup-

port after the reaction monitored by tlc and washed thoroughly with methanol. The washed solid (solid mixture) was dried, activated under vacuum (reported previously) and used for further reaction. The reaction of aniline and acetyl chloride was tested for successive runs without any considerable decrease in the yield of the corresponding acetylated product or loss of activity of the solid surface. Similarly, recycling of the silica magnesium oxide mixed surface is also tested for seven consecutive runs without any loss of its activity taking the reaction of benzyl alcohol and acetyl chloride as a representative example (Tables 5 and 6). Moreover, scaling up the reactions to 1 mol scale also showed the same reactivity.

The already reported mechanism⁵⁸⁻⁶¹ for the surface activity of silica, when used as a support in a solid phase mediated reaction, may also be considered here in explaining the above findings.

Table 5 Recycling experiments using aniline and acetyl chloride-promoted over silica surface

Sl. no.	Run	Yield of <i>N</i> -acyl aniline (%)
1.	1st	94
2.	2nd	94
3.	3rd	92
4.	4th	90
5.	5th	88
6.	6th	92
7.	7th	90

% Yield refers to the isolated yield of the product.

Table 6. Recycling experiments using benzyl alcohol and acetyl chloride promoted over silica-magnesia surface

Sl. no.	Run	Yield of <i>o</i> -acyl benzyl alcohol (%)
1	1st	78
2	2nd	76
3	3rd	78
4	4th	80
5	5th	76
6	6th	74
7	7th	78

% Yield refers to the isolated yield of the product.

Experimental

General procedure for synthesis of amides :

Preactivated silica gel (500 mg) was taken in a round bottom flask and 2 mmol of amine was added to it and the mixture was agitated with a magnetic spinning bar to make the mixture homogeneous. Then 2 mmol of acid chloride (previously weighed) was added dropwise to the mixture of silica gel and amine with continuous stirring. The reaction mixture was then allowed to stir at room temperature until the reaction was over (monitored by tlc). After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was washed repeatedly by suitable solvent (ethyl acetate or methanol) and the combined washings was concentrated and purified by either crystallisation or column chromatography using silica gel (60–120 mesh). The pure products obtained were characterised by ^1H , ^{13}C NMR, IR and also with comparing literature melting points.

General procedure for synthesis of esters :

For *O*-acylation of alcohols 1 : 1 silica gel magnesium oxide mixture was made by mixing equal amount of both

the solids by weight in distilled THF and stirred for 30 min at room temperature and then evaporated, dried under vacuum. Then the solid mixture was activated at 200 °C under vacuum until bubbling ceases. 500 mg preactivated solid mixture was taken in a round bottom flask and 1 mmol of alcohol was added to it and the mixture was agitated with a magnetic spinning bar to make the mixture homogeneous. Then 1 mmol of acid chloride (previously weighed) was added dropwise to the mixture of silica gel and alcohol with continuous stirring. The reaction mixture was then allowed to stir at room temperature until the reaction was over (monitored by tlc). After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was washed repeatedly by suitable solvent (ethyl acetate or methanol) and the combined washings was concentrated and purified by either crystallisation or column chromatography using silica gel (60–120 mesh). The pure products obtained were characterised by ^1H , ^{13}C NMR, IR and also with comparing literature melting points.

Conclusions :

A very simple, mild, chemoselective and environmentally benign procedure has been developed for *N* and *O*-acylation, benzoylation, chloroacetylation and sulfonylation of various types of amines and alcohols. The invention which is greener and cost effective may also be used by the pharmaceutical industries for the bulk production of reaction of intermediates as well as the finished products.

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